

The history learning module integrated character values

Jems Sopacua, Muhammad Rijal Fadli, Saefur Rochmat
Graduate School, Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The history learning module integrated character values is an innovation in history learning in schools to support educational progress. This module serves as teaching material for the process of character formation of students obtained through independent learning to achieve the desired competency goals. This research uses the development (R&D) of the 4D model (define, design, development and dissemination). The results showed that the module was declared feasible based on the results of the validation of the experts, so the modules that had been developed were feasible, effective and practical to be used as teaching materials and learning resources by students in the history learning process. This module has the advantage that there are character values (love of the motherland, curiosity, religious and tolerance) in the material presented for the formation of students' character.

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Corresponding Author:

Jems Sopacua,
Graduate School, Department of History Education,
Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta,
Jl. Colombo No.1, Karang Malang, Caturtunggal, Kec. Depok, Sleman, Yogyakarta, Indonesia.
Email: jems.sopacua7@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

The influence of globalization has at least pushed the character and character of students who experience drastic changes to produce a generation that can face the global cultural clash that confronts the younger generation. The influence of globalization for the young generation holds many hopes and worries that have a psychological impact because it necessitates a decision to choose a way of life that is by the prevailing norms in society. The progress of science and technology which is reflected by the influence of globalization will at least undermine the order of moral values of students who are not equipped with good character so that it can be fatal to the mental and mental maturity of students [1].

The learning process must be able to support students to become humans who face the development of the times. Today's ongoing globalization leads to post-modern culture [2]. The development of science and technology makes the world seem limitless so that this condition impacts the lives of people, the nation, and the state. Also, it affects the mindset, attitude patterns, and behavior in society. Current globalization has an impact on the moral degradation of the nation [3]. As a result of the globalization of the strategic environment is currently developing rapidly, namely the occurrence of a moral crisis in students [4].

During various problems that hit our nation today, ranging from conflicts, brawls, drugs, acts of terrorism, corruption to violence in the world of education. Following with Suparjan [5] that this is a symptom of the fading character and identity of Indonesia. So we need a new formulation in the world of education so that the character of the next generation is really tough in facing the progress of the times.

Education has faced a dilemma problem, on the one hand, teachers have gained welfare through certification allowances, school facilities are getting more and more luxurious with almost nothing lacking in terms of infrastructure. Outstanding student achievement [6]. However, on the other hand, the character and

morality of students are increasingly degraded. This study will provide a solution by developing teaching materials in the form of modules that are integrated with character values [7]. The goal is that the learning process of history has an impact and role model for students to guide and enlighten during turmoil and moral dryness in generations.

The need to instill character values is a must for every nation. Given that the current threat to the loss of national identity is a real threat. The process of investing in values can be done through education by forming the nation's character. In line with Syaifulloh [8], this has been declared by President Jokowi, the national movement of the mental revolution. A strong character can encourage and realize actions that have the character as well. This means that the mental revolution promoted by President Jokowi signifies the problem of a character crisis that enters a chronic stage. This certainly has an impact on the decline of the nation's personality [9]. The use of the three pillars of the Trisakti concept (sovereign, independent, and personality) in the mental revolution proves that history, which has provided a picture of events over of time, is not dead, but is still alive and has its relevance in the present and the future.

Indonesian national figures before the birth of the Indonesian state had fought and were willing to sacrifice for the future. Gonggong explains that thinking far beyond his time has provided full proof of the importance of good character and qualified [10]. Like planting a tree that reaps not directly picked but reaped in the future. That is to learn history is very important so that a nation knows the process of the birth of a warrior character. Indonesia is built, created, and maintained by people of character.

The field of history education has a position as one of the subjects that can be used to shape the nation's character (nation and character-building). Historical subjects can be used as a solution as an internalization of character values to develop a national identity in facing the challenges of globalization today. Learning history has an important role in shaping the personality of students to be able to understand and implement character values [11]. The contribution of history learning can instill students' historical awareness so that it can be reflected in today's life [12].

The purpose of learning history in the current era of globalization must be to prepare students who have quality and character [13, 14]. Learning history for students is very important because it can help to think more critically and wisely, and be able to understand the meaning and value of every past event to prepare for the future, not just remembering characters, facts and years [15, 16]. Thus, the purpose of learning history is not limited to the cognitive domain (knowledge) but can reach the psychomotor domain in the process of character formation of students.

Historical learning with character values is the result of a very suitable combination because historical learning has a role as an effort to form characters and instill cultural values. Aman [17] explains that the purpose of learning history is to instill a spirit of nationalism, love of the motherland, tolerance, and historical awareness. Also, learning history functions to make students aware of the process of change and development of society in the time dimension and build perspectives in finding, understanding, and explaining the national identity in the past, present, and future during the development of the times [18]. The internalization of character values in learning history is a necessity. This is because historical learning has the potential as a medium for transmitting character values through past and exemplary events.

In the process of embedding the nation's character values, history learning must be designed in such a way, not only as a transfer of knowledge but also a transfer of value, so that it can design historical learning that interests students [19, 20]. Now, this has developed a breakthrough in innovations in learning, namely the presence of teaching materials in the form of modules that can facilitate students in understanding historical material [21]. The learning module is a teaching material that contains material, methods, and evaluations that are systematically designed that can be used independently by students to achieve the expected competencies.

The purpose of the learning module is for independent learners to be facilitated by the teacher. In line with Dhaliwal, Simpson & Kim-Sing [22] explaining that there were challenges in the development, implementation, and evaluation of this project. There was a substantial amount of information on experiential education and teaching in the experiential setting that could have been conveyed in each of the modules. The development of independent learning skills makes students better understand the subject matter and practice their skills. Molenaar, Horvers, & Baker [23] explained that ultimately to develop self-regulated learning skills. Also, teachers could potentially use a diagnostic tool to analyze which students need support. The purpose of the module can also develop students' competence further. In line with Enke, Kraft, & Metternich explained that learning is a module is to develop the right competencies further [24].

The success of innovations developed can support the advancement of education. But it does not stop there, the teacher must play a role in every learning process for the advancement of education. The role of the teacher in this case, is very important, because teachers are required to be creative to create more enjoyable learning. Modules can be used as a medium in the delivery of learning materials, with the presence of good learning media that can support the creation of a good learning process as well. Through good learning media, teachers can make learning history more real, so that media that are designed attractively can increase

students' interest in learning, instill character values and add insight to learners' knowledge to achieve learning objectives.

This study aimed to develop an integrated history learning module of character values. Following the 2013 (revised) curriculum, character education is very important to be applied, but there are no teaching materials available that integrate character values into historical material to support existing textbooks. The integrated history learning module character values will give students an overview of the material history of the entry of Islam into Indonesia which is integrated with the values of the nation's character. The character values that can be integrated into the historical material of the entry of Islam in Indonesia include the love of the motherland, curiosity, religion, and tolerance.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research used the method of Research and Development (R&D) with the define, design, develop, and dissemination (4D) model [25, 26]. The research objective is to produce an integrated history learning module product of character values. The 4D development model through four steps, namely the definition, design, development, and dissemination [27]. An overview of the procedures performed in using the 4D development model is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. 4D development model

This research was conducted at MAN 1 Metro Lampung involving 69 students (25 trials 1 and 44 trials 2). The subjects in this study were class XI MAN 1 Metro Lampung. Sampling-based on high, medium, and low ranking categories, in the sampling using random sampling techniques. During the two stages of the trial students who become respondents differ. This development research focuses on product feasibility testing, due diligence is carried out to experts namely material expert validation, media expert validation, validation by teachers and students.

Data collection techniques used were interviews and assessment questionnaires related to the product developed. While the data analysis technique is done using qualitative data analysis techniques and quantitative data [28, 29]. Quantitative data were obtained from a questionnaire that was converted to qualitative data with a Likert scale of 5 to know the feasibility of the product being developed, with the guidelines [30] shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Guidelines for converting quantitative data scores to qualitative data

No	Score Interval	Score	Category	Range
1.	Very Decent	A	$X > \bar{X} + 1.80 S_{bi}$	$X > 4.20$
2.	Decent	B	$\bar{X} + 0.60 S_{bi} < X \leq + 0.60 S_{bi}$	$3.40 < X \leq 4.20$
3.	Decent Enough	C	$\bar{X} - 0.60 S_{bi} < X \leq \bar{X} + 0.60 S_{bi}$	$2.60 < X \leq 3.40$
4.	Inadequate	D	$\bar{X} - 1.80 S_{bi} < X \leq - 0.60 S_{bi}$	$1.80 < X \leq 2.60$
5.	Very Inadequate	E	$X \leq \bar{X} - 1.80 S_{bi}$	$X \leq 1.80$

Information:

- X = Actual Score (score obtained)
- \bar{X} = (Ideal Average)
 $= \frac{1}{2} (\text{Maximum Score} + \text{Minimum Score})$
 $= \frac{1}{2} (5+1) = 3$
- S_{bi} = (Ideal Standard Deviation)
 $= \frac{1}{6} (\text{Maximum Score} + \text{Minimum Score})$
 $= \frac{1}{6} (5-1) = 0.67$

Based on the table on score conversion, the standard of learning history from each aspect is obtained as a standard with details very feasible if the average score obtained is in the range of 4.21 to 5.00 with the category "A". Eligible if the average score obtained is a range of 3.41 to 4.20 with the category "B". Fair enough if the average score obtained is a range of 2.61 to 3.40 with the category "C". Not feasible if the average score obtained is a range of 1.81 to 2.60 with the category "D". Very less feasible if the average score obtained is in the range of less than 1.80 with the category "E".

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Result

Based on development research conducted, that the product of this development is in the form of an integrated history learning module of character values. The process is carried out by the 4D development model adopted from Thiagarajan with stages: 1) Define; 2) Design; 3) Development; 4) Dissemination. The steps are as follows:

3.1.1. Define phase

At this stage, researchers conduct a needs analysis related to the modules developed. The needs analysis that has been done in the field study and literature study. Analysis of the field study was carried out by conducting unstructured observations and interviews with teachers and students. While the literature study is carried out to obtain related learning history studies and learning modules. At this defining stage, the researcher analyzes from the curriculum to historical material that can be integrated with character values. The material developed is the historical material of the entry of Islam in Indonesia which is contained in the basic competencies 3.2.

3.1.2. Design phase

This design phase researchers gather the information that can be used as a support in the development of history learning modules that are developed. The data collected is adjusted to the 2013 curriculum and then to the competency standard of history lessons, then summarized in the form of a draft temporary module. Modules are developed systematically with the suitability found in the study of literature. The steps taken at this design stage are to submit an initial draft module. Submitting the initial draft of this module with several stages including 1) Analyzing KI and KD with the material in the module, 2) Analyzing learning objectives, 3) Analyzing learning materials, and 4) Analyzing learning evaluations.

At this design stage, the module design activities that are developed include: 1) Making the initial draft of the material integrated with character values, 2) Choosing interesting images to be used in the module, 3) Making questions related to the material in the module, 4) Preparation of the glossary, the key answers to the questions contained in the module, 5) The design of the module cover used to describe the module contents.

3.1.3. Development phase

At this stage of development, it produces the final module (product) after going through the stages of validating the experts and revising it according to the advice of the experts. This stage is included from the realization of the previous stages so that the initial draft module framework is compiled, designed, equipped, and made into actual modules. The development of an integrated history learning module character values of the entry of Islam in Indonesia was developed and designed using the help of Photoshop and Corel Draw programs with pdf format before printing. Module components consist of cover modules, module identity, preface, core competencies, basic competencies and indicators, learning objectives, module usage instructions, concept maps, learning activities 1 and 2 which contain a description of the material, a summary of each learning activity, assignments in each learning activity, formative tests in each learning activity, evaluation questions/final project, answer key, glossary, bibliography, author biography.

At this stage, the researcher validates the initial product to the material expert, media expert, and history teacher. Validation to the history teacher is carried out after passing the validation from the material experts and media experts after everything is done it will do a limited trial first before field trials. The results of the validation from the experts will be used as a revision/improvement of the initial product that has been developed. Validation is done to find out the feasibility of the module, as for the validation steps as follows:

3.1.3.1. Material expert validation

This material validation includes aspects of the relevance of the material in the integrated history learning module character values developed by researchers. The assessment data was obtained from the results of the questionnaire contents with a Likert scale of 5 (1-5) that had been provided by researchers, the questionnaire consisted of 24 assessment indicators and there were 3 aspects. The results of the material expert validation can be seen briefly based on the recapitulation of the material expert judgment presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of expert material validation

No	Assessment aspects	Total value	Average value	Category
1.	Fill in the material	37	4.6	Very decent
2.	Material presentation design	53	4.8	Very decent
3.	Linguistic	22	4.4	Very decent
	Total	112	4.66	Very decent

Based on the table of results of the expert validation of the material above after being converted from quantitative data into qualitative data, the results obtained with an average score (X) of 4.66. The average score is included in the range $X > 4.20$, meaning that the integrated history learning module product value developed based on the validation of material experts is included in the criteria of value A with the category "Very Decent". This means that the module is worth testing by material experts. The recapitulation of the results of the material expert validation is presented in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. Diagram of material expert validation results

3.1.3.2. Media expert validation

Media expert validation is done after the product design stage is complete. Module media validation is done to determine the feasibility of the media contained in the module before testing. The assessment conducted by the validation of media experts related to the history learning module integrated the character values including the module graphics and the module content design that has been developed by the researcher. The history learning module media expert at this stage fills in the questionnaire prepared by the researcher with a choice of 5 Likert scales (1-5), the number of questions there are 27 assessment indicators, and 3 aspects. Recapitulation of the results of the validation of media experts can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Media expert validation results

No	Assessment aspects	Total value	Average value	Category
1.	Graphical	46	4.6	Very decent
2.	Module content design	56	4.3	Very decent
3.	Linguistic	17	4.2	Very decent
	Total	119	4.40	Very decent

Based on the results table the validation of media experts obtained results with an average score (X) in the range $X > 4.20$. Obtaining the results of the validation of the learning module media expert integrated character values with an average value of 4.40 included in the value criteria A "Very Decent". This means that history learning modules by media experts are declared worthy to be tested according to the suggestions and comments that have been given by media experts. The recapitulation of the results from the validation of media experts is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Diagram of media expert validation results

3.1.3.3. Teacher validation

The history learning module integrated character values before being trialed to students was validated beforehand by the history teacher, to fit the criteria in history learning at school. The questionnaire assessed by the teacher contained 25 questions and 3 aspects of the assessment indicators. The results of teacher validation can be seen from the Table 4.

Table 4. Teacher validation results

No	Assessment aspects	Total value	Average value	Category
1.	Presentation of content	40	4.4	Very decent
2.	Module content design	51	4.6	Very decent
3.	Linguistic	21	4.2	Very decent
	Total	112	4.48	Very decent

Based on the validation conducted by researchers on history subject teachers have obtained results with an average score of (X) 4.48 which falls in the range of $X > 4.20$. This means that the results of the score from the history teacher's validation fall into the category A "Very Decent" so that the modules that have been developed are worth testing for students. Recapitulation of the results of validation by the teacher is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Diagram of the results of validation by the teacher

3.1.3.4. Dissemination phase

In this Dissemination phase, a trial module has been developed, in which the trial is carried out twice, considering that before testing it on a large scale it needs to be tested with the limited aim of knowing the responses of some students, involving 25 students. While the 2nd trial (field) was conducted in class XI MAN 1 Metro Social Sciences and Natural Sciences program involving 44 students. Trial 1 or limited trials are conducted after obtaining validation from experts. The first trial has involved 25 students of class XI IPA 2, the aim is to determine the initial response of students in responding to the modules that have been developed. The questionnaire distributed was 23 assessment questions and 3 aspects of the assessment indicators. The results of trial 1 can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Student’s trial responses 1 (limited test)

No	Assessment aspects	Total value	Average value	Category
1.	Presentation of content	974	4.2	Very decent
2.	Module content design	1141	4.3	Very decent
3.	Linguistic	757	4.3	Very decent
	Total	112	4.33	Very decent

The results of responses from students to the modules that have been disseminated in the learning process are converted from quantitative data into qualitative data, the results obtained with an average score (X) of 4.33. This means that the score is included in the range of scores $X > 4.20$, which means the module products get an A with the category "Very Decent". Thus, the module that has been tested in the first phase has received a very positive response and the module is suitable for use as a learning resource.

In the trial stage, 2 (field) students will assess the feasibility of the product that has been developed by researchers to be implemented. The results of trial 2 or field trials have become the final stages of the application of the development of an integrated history learning module of character values. The purpose of this field test is to find out if the module developed is feasible to be implemented in the history learning process in schools. The responses of students in trial phase 2 (field) can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Student’s trial responses 2 (field test)

No	Assessment aspects	Total value	Average value	Category
1.	Presentation of content	1687	4.4	Very decent
2.	Module content design	2000	4.5	Very decent
3.	Linguistic	1349	4.6	Very decent
	Total	5036	4.52	Very decent

Table 6 explains that the results of the responses of students in the trial phase 2 (field) have obtained an average score of 4.52, meaning that a score $(X) > 4.20$, which means included in the category of "Very Good". So the modules that have been developed based on the responses of trial 1 and trial 2, get very positive responses from students, so the modules developed are suitable for use as media and learning resources in the history learning process in schools. Recapitulation of the results of the dissemination of modules to students can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Student’s responses

3.2. Discussion

The results of the dissemination of modules, trials 1 and 2 show that the modules that have been developed are suitable for use as media and learning resources in the history learning process. The module developed has its value, because in the module it is integrated with character values. The character values that are instilled are the love of the motherland, curiosity, religion, and tolerance.

The history learning module can be said to be feasible if it meets the quality aspects of validity, practicality, and effectiveness [31, 32]. The results obtained indicate that the module developed is feasible. The integrated history learning module character values are appropriate to be used to support the achievement of national education goals. Also, in research Trisnawati [33] teaching materials in the form of integrated modules are very decent, practical, and effective character values used in history learning to help the character building of students.

The results of the validation carried out by experts indicate that the module in this research is appropriate for use in the history learning process. The validation results from each expert obtained a good and positive response. Judging from the results of the acquisition of material expert validation with an average value of 4.66, 4.40 media experts, 4.48 history teachers, and 4.53 field trials. Based on the results of the validation, this history learning module is very feasible to use. This is reinforced by Sukardjo [34] which states that in every development research that produces a product at least the acquisition of validation from experts is in the range of scores $X > 4.20$ with a very decent category. While these study results were obtained with an average value above the range of scores $X > 4.20$ so that the module is feasible to use. In line with Diani research [35] which produces integrated modules, character values are suitable for use in the learning process and can also be used to support the achievement of basic competencies, indicators, meet quality standard criteria and can assist in the process of character building for students who have been determined.

Based on the results of previous research related to the development of modules in the history of learning integrated character values Subekti [36] shows that the product developed is very effective and suitable for use as material teaching in the learning process. The difference with previous research is in the product and the character values listed. The module that the researcher developed has a striking character in historical material that is integrated with 4 character values, namely homeland love, curiosity, religion, and tolerance so that this module cannot form other character values.

The integrated history learning module research of character values needs to be continuously developed and innovated to be in harmony with life in the current era of globalization. Especially in the current era of globalization has experienced a moral crisis that occurs among the younger generation, then the focus of attention is related to the strengthening of character education because character education can help to direct and shape the character of students to become wise people.

The novelty contained in this study is to produce a module with the material for the entry of Islam into Indonesia which is integrated with certain character values. With the integrated history learning module, character values can help the process of character formation of students in the current rapid globalization. This study compares with Kuswono & Khaeroni [37] research where the research he conducted produced a module together, but the character values included were only one value, namely religious. Whereas in this study the character values that are integrated with the material there are 4 values namely (patriotism, curiosity, religion, and tolerance).

Thus, character education with the process of learning history cannot be separated just like that. Because it is necessary to do a series of efforts to improve the learning process-oriented to the development of character education [38]. Character education can be done by integrating character values in history learning. Integrating character values into history learning is done through efficient and meaningful learning for students [39]. Although, to integrate character values into history learning is not easy. But that is a breakthrough that needs to be increased in the investment of education, especially history.

The integrated history learning module character values are appropriate to be used in the learning process. In this case, the development of history learning modules should continue to be done to be able to add variety and development as teaching materials and learning resources for history. Such research is conducted by Maslahah & Rofiah [40] who have developed historical teaching materials with different variations for historical development and progress. Therefore, new developments and innovations in history are needed to facilitate students in understanding history so that students are interested and interested in history lessons so that students' negative assumptions about history that tend to be boring turn into positive assumptions.

4. CONCLUSION

The integrated history learning module character values are suitable to be used as teaching materials and learning resources in history learning. Modules that have been validated by material experts, media experts, teachers, and students have obtained very positive results, so that the integrated history learning module has character values that have been declared feasible, practical, and effective for use in history learning. The implication of the integrated history learning module is that character values are expected to be able to contribute to adding new insights to students in terms of the character values that have been listed and can be applied in everyday life. This module can also be used in history learning activities and can also be used to increase students' knowledge horizons. In addition, researchers hope that the innovations in learning history can change the negative views of students towards history that only learns the past and tends to be boring, become interested, and interesting in learning history. This research only focuses on feasibility, so that in the future it can be continued until the effectiveness test to find out whether there are developments related to the character of students who are implanted.

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